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DEVELOPMENT OF BIOCLIMATIC MODELING OF ARCHITECTURE AND DESIGN OBJECTS IN THE MODERN INFORMATION ENVIRONMENT

Abstract.

The development of bioclimatic modeling of architectural and design objects is one of the effective directions for the implementation of ecological energy-saving design solutions. The main feature of bioclimatic modeling is finding ways to optimize the interaction of architectural and design objects with natural and climatic factors, which requires relevant knowledge in the field of climatology, materials science, production processes, energy auditing and management, control systems, and, of course, architecture and design. In other words, it involves working with large amounts of information and data, which requires an understanding of the capabilities and means of the modern information environment for the effective implementation of bioclimatic modeling. Therefore, it is important to analyze and determine the directions for the development of bioclimatic modeling of architectural and design objects in modern conditions, which are characterized by the active development of digital competencies.

The article discusses the stages of implementation of digital technologies in architectural design and design, which is associated with the computerization and formation of the information environment in the second half of the 20th century. The analysis presented in the study concerns the determination of the possibilities of introducing bioclimatic modeling in the design of architectural and design objects at various stages of the development of the information environment: from the emergence of computer-aided design (CAD) information systems, the use of CAE/CAD/CAM digital technologies, to the current stage associated with the development of "artificial intelligence."

The conclusion was reached that the solution to the multi-parameter problem of creating bioclimatic modeling of architectural and design objects based on taking into account climatic and natural parameters of the environment, expected characteristics of objects, in compliance with the requirements of sustainable development and energy efficiency, can be implemented within the framework of an expert system belonging to the class of intelligent systems. Based on the consideration of the principles of the expert system, the possibility of solving bioclimatic modeling problems in accordance with the functions and parameters of the data that should form its basis has been determined.

Keywords: bioclimatic modeling, information environment, expert systems, architecture and design objects.

Problem Statement. Analysis of Recent Research and Publications

Energy and resource conservation and sustainable use of natural resources are major trends in the modern world. The bioclimatic approach is one of the effective directions of modeling environmentally friendly energy-saving design solutions. The main feature of bioclimatic modeling is finding ways to optimize the interaction of architectural and design objects with climatic factors (solar radiation, wind, temperature, humidity, etc.) [1–3]. Such solutions lead to a reduction in the base level of energy consumption and, accordingly, energy conservation, and contribute to a reduction in the negative impact on the surrounding natural environment and climate [3].

For bioclimatic modeling of architectural and design objects, it is necessary to take into account multifaceted factors, which requires relevant knowledge in the field of climatology, materials science, production processes, energy auditing and management, control systems, and, of course,

architecture and design. In other words, this involves working with large amounts of information and data, which requires an understanding of the capabilities and means of the modern information environment for the effective implementation of bioclimatic modeling in architecture and design.

The advent of the Fourth Industrial Revolution at the beginning of the 21st century is associated with global computerization processes and is defined by the modern "post-digital" stage. This stage of social transformation is characterized by the active development of digital competencies, which are embodied in the main spheres of society's life [4].

The new conditions of the digital environment require an updated integrated approach to interacting with reality and the application of innovative technologies in shaping the physical and information-communication environment, which in turn is the basis for the implementation of effective bioclimatic modeling solutions [5].

In a broad sense, the information environment is understood as the world of information surrounding a person and the sphere of their information activity [6]. In this sense, the information environment is part of the noosphere, a concept introduced by Ukrainian scientist M. Vernadsky, related to human activity [4]. The concept of "information environment" can also refer to an individual, a group of people, and be a parameter of their information activity [7], and currently, artificial intelligent systems that also process information logically and autonomously [5]. In a narrower sense, the information environment is a set of technical and software means for storing, processing, and transmitting information, as well as the political, economic, and cultural conditions for the implementation of informatization processes. [8]. It is in this applied sense, related to the development of computer technologies, that this concept is considered in many scientific studies and in this article.

Purpose of the Article. To analyze and identify directions for the development of bioclimatic modeling of architectural and design objects in the modern information environment.

Presentation of the main material.

The introduction of digital technologies in architectural design and design is associated with computerization and the formation of the information environment in the second half of the 20th century. The information environment as a social phenomenon has gone through several stages of development.

The emergence of the information environment began in the 1950s-1970s, from theoretical justification to practical implementation, associated with the transfer of data from the analog to the digital sphere [6]. The 1980s and 1990s were characterized by the rapid development of information technologies, globalization, and the digitization of all spheres of human activity. Since the 2000s, human society has been undergoing a transformation under the influence of information technologies, and a global information and communication environment has emerged [5].

Before the advent of the digital age, the processes of design and modeling in architecture and design were based on manual drawing, which required significant resource costs. The advent of computer-aided design (CAD) systems revolutionized the process of developing architectural and design solutions by offering digital ways to solve them.

Revolutionary examples of the use of computer technology in building architecture were the composition on the Olympic waterfront in Barcelona (1992) and the Guggenheim Museum of Modern Art in Bilbao (1997) by architect F. Gehry, when CAD programs, which had previously been used only for applied rather than creative purposes, were used to calculate the curved outlines of objects. It is believed that the design of Frank Gehry's objects using traditional manual drawing would not have been as successful as it was thanks to engineering technologies [9].

At the same time, CAD software of that period did not include functions related to energy efficiency and environmental design.

The next important stage in the development of digital tools for architectural design and design was the development of the global Internet network. CAE/CAD/CAM systems became widespread in the field of design. This abbreviation stands for Computer Aided Engineering/Computer Aided Design/Computer Aided Manufacturing. CAE is the name of software designed to solve engineering problems: calculations, analysis of behavior, product and simulation of physical processes, such as structural strength, load, stress, deformation, analysis of thermal processes, calculation of hydraulic systems and mechanisms. Such computer modeling technologies, together with CPP and 3D printing, have provided new opportunities for the development of architectural and object design, which can be attributed to bioclimatic modeling tools. For example, when modeling clothing adapted to changes in physical parameters, using a special thermoregulating textile structure or adding functional materials for the production of fibers or fabrics (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Thermo-regulating textiles, manufactured on the basis of 3D-design, which ensures energy-saving conditions in clothing [10]

The use of CAE/CAD/CAM digital technologies is growing rapidly around the world. For example, China has introduced a state program called the "National Plan for the Promotion of Computer Technology Development" [11]. This and other documents provide for the expansion of digital technologies and their integration into manufacturing.

BIM (Building Information Modeling) technology is used in the design of buildings and structures. Information modeling of structures is an object-oriented model of a building object in three dimensions (3D model), with data on the geometric, physical, and functional characteristics of the building object [12]. A distinctive feature of BIM technology is the creation of an information model of a construction object (its digital description), which allows for the optimization of designers' actions.

VIM is constantly improving: the technology has been expanded with the addition of time (4D) and cost (5D) indicators. The 4D virtual model tracks and controls the floor-by-floor construction process, while simultaneously visualizing the building for a selected period of time; 5D enables the creation of more accurate cost estimates and cost control. The introduction of the sixth dimension (6D) of BIM is expected, representing aspects of the environment and sustainability of buildings, compliance with the principles of sustainable development in the construction process. The technology allows you to evaluate a building design in terms of energy conservation, use of solar energy, etc. The seventh dimension (7D) of BIM consists of managing the operation of the facility throughout its entire service life [13].

Thus, BIM software is developing in the direction of taking into account natural and climatic factors in design. For this purpose, data from geographic information systems (GIS) are used, which are software products that display a digital map of the area at the global, regional, or local level.

Autodesk is implementing a pilot project to integrate various GIS with Autodesk BIM, which allows for more accurate consideration of natural conditions in design. For example, Autodesk's InfraWorks CAD software has been integrated with Hydronia GIS, which makes it possible to simulate, visualize, and animate a 3D model of flooding in cities, ultimately allowing the development of design

solutions to prevent or mitigate the impact of natural disasters in urban areas. The Green Stormwater Infrastructure add-on for InfraWorks allows you to quickly create and analyze rainwater runoff control projects in real time to determine the best way to place objects.

If, at an earlier stage of technological development, the computer became one of the working tools for designers, in the modern era, information systems are taking on the characteristics of collaborative creativity with humans with the development of "artificial intelligence" (AI). Information systems are becoming not only effective assistants, but also co-authors in the creation of architectural and design objects. The foundations have been laid for computer systems to assist humans in performing design tasks.

Numerous studies by scientists and practitioners of information technologies have formed the basis for computer systems to assist humans in performing creative tasks, including design. In particular, AI uses basic structural design elements such as "primitives" when constructing objects in many areas. Assistive design technology is based on these elements. There are quite a few assistive technologies, for example, technical solutions directly related to product design, such as autofocus devices for capturing images, device screens with auto-correction of color and brightness, auto-correction photo programs, photo and video coloring programs, assisted design of 3D models of industrial objects, the formation of clothing patterns for creating 3D models, medical equipment for people with disabilities, and many others. The leaders in the development of assistive technologies are the United States and China [14].

At the intersection of such cutting-edge areas of AI as machine learning (ML), human-computer interaction (HCI), neural networks, and design, a tool known as generative design has become widespread. It emerged as a further development of assistive design, but is more flexible and autonomous.

The principle of generative design is the independent, human-free generation of AI design technical solutions according to specified parameters, and the designer's function is to make the final choice from several generated objects that are optimal in terms of characteristics (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. "Tectonics of Materials" series, designer Daniel Baloyan. The design solutions for the facade of the building are developed using Midjourney Ai - artificial intelligence [15]

Within the scope of research and development of technologies for using artificial intelligence software tools that perform creative functions, a separate scientific field of expert systems has emerged and is developing. An expert system (ES) is a program that uses the knowledge of specialists (experts) in a specific, highly specialized subject area and is capable of making decisions at the level of a professional expert within that field [16].

A feature of ES is the ability to accumulate the knowledge and experience of the most experienced experts in a narrow subject area that requires a creative approach, and to provide recommendations for decision-making. The system stores rules for solving problems in a specific problem area in knowledge bases. The problem is presented to the system in the form of a set of facts describing a certain situation. The system then uses the knowledge base to attempt to draw conclusions from these facts, just as an expert would.

Thus, EC users who are learning or have average qualifications can solve their current tasks at a high level. This effect is achieved because the ES uses a reasoning scheme in its work that an expert would use in a given situation, which makes it possible to store, accumulate, and disseminate knowledge, making the

unique experience of professional experts available to a wide range of ordinary specialists [17].

ES differs from other artificial intelligence programs in that it deals with real-world objects in a specific field, operations with which require the use of a significant amount of experience and explanation of the validity of the decision made. The authors [16] identify certain classes of decision-making tasks for which the development of ES is the most suitable system.

An example of an expert system that takes climatic factors into account is Web Flex [18], which determines the productivity of plants used for afforestation in a specific geographical area, on a specific soil, in the surrounding natural conditions, on a yield scale. Similarly, ES can be applied to bioclimatic modeling of decisions in architecture and design. In this case, it is expected to perform the following generalized functions: analyze and classify bioclimatic solutions; identify and interpret information about the compliance of certain solutions with the characteristics of the bioclimatic approach; diagnose problems and predict the results of applying the bioclimatic approach; train specialists and learn (acquire new knowledge), Table 1.

Table 1.

Assessing the relevance of ES and bioclimatic modeling tasks

N	Task class	Characteristics of the task class	Coincidence with bioclimatic modeling tasks
1.	Tasks of forecasting and classification	Involve a large number (>10) of possible solutions	Yes
2.	Multiparametric problems	The complexity of determining analytical dependencies	Yes
3.	Tasks that require expert professional training	Practical tasks that cannot be solved using classical methods	Yes
4.	Tasks involving the processing of inaccurate information	The solution to the problem is based on the use of operations with symbols - the problem is not related to mathematical calculations, does not have a clear algorithmic expression, but involves logical analysis and selection of options	Partially, "yes"

In general, the use of an expert system for bioclimatic modeling of architectural and design objects, without the need for human intervention, allows for the automation of data analysis, modeling, and decision-making processes, which reduces the negative impact on the environment and ecological load and significantly improves the energy efficiency of design objects.

This is relevant for China, which is located in climatic zones 1-12, and the country's natural conditions are undergoing significant changes in latitudinal and meridional directions [19]. The creation of bioclimatic objects in such variable natural and climatic conditions requires taking into account climatic characteristics, a significant number of object parameters, and the application of appropriate design solutions in the design, which can be solved with the help of an intelligent system capable of processing a large number of parameters (multiple climatic and natural conditions, characteristics of design object elements) and recommending optimal bioclimatic solutions.

The peculiarity of expert systems as a direction of AI is that they model human activity, which is carried out in an informal way for multi-parameter tasks, which is characteristic of bioclimatic modeling. While methods for solving computational problems are based on clear algorithms, knowledge representation models in expert systems deal with information obtained from experts, which is often qualitative and heterogeneous in nature. At the same time, the need for such models is felt in virtually all subject areas of architecture and design. This explains the need to build an expert system for bioclimatic modeling, determined by the specifics of the subject area of architecture and design [20].

Conclusions. Based on the study of the development and implementation of digital design technologies, it was concluded that most software tools do not implement the function of bioclimatic modeling. The solution of the multi-parameter problem of creating bioclimatic modeling of architectural and design objects based on taking into account climatic and natural parameters of the environment, expected characteristics of objects, in compliance with the requirements of sustainable development and energy efficiency, can be implemented within the framework of an expert system belonging to the class of intelligent systems, which will provide support for decision-making by the designer [20]. Based on consideration of the principles of the expert system, the possibility of developing solutions for bioclimatic modeling tasks in accordance with the functions and parameters of the data that should form its basis has been determined.

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